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COVID-19 PANDEMIC AND THE HOSPITALITY AND TOURISM INDUSTRY IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

COVID-19 pandemic which shocked the World originated from Wuhan, China in late 2019 and spread to other countries of the World. According to World Health Organization, (WHO) over 200 countries were affected and more than 5,000,000 (Five million people) died from COVID-19 pandemic. Nigeria, was not spared the impact of the pandemic as a traveller from Italy visited Nigeria and brought the infection into the country. In the wake of the pandemic's spread in Nigeria, the Federal Government of Nigeria mandated a general lock-down which included the closure of airports, both Local and International Airports. Events were cancelled or postponed. Attractions and Entertainment such as Sport Activities were postponed for extended periods of time. Also, the Hotel Industry, Restaurants and Markets were forced to lock-down from the reach of the public. Individuals were forced to stay home. Many employees were laid off from work. The general lock-down was later relaxed to restrictions on Travels and Airports. Hospitality Industry was largely impacted by the lock-downs and restrictions. How did the Hospitality Industry face the challenges of the pandemic and has the industry bounced back? This Paper seeks to answer that question.

KEYWORDS

COVID-19 Pandemic, Hospitality, Lock-down, Restrictions.

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Introduction

The outbreak of Coronavirus also known as COVID-19 pandemic affected the normal activities of everyday living Worldwide. Nigeria was not left out. Ollor, (2012) have said how individuals live in a network, interdependent, and united by global economy. The above statement could be appropriated to how the whole World is globally netted as a community; individuals could travel back and forth using different routes to places of their destinations. Means of travels could be by road, rail, sea or by air, (Roday, Biwal, and Joshi, 2009); (Ghosh, 2008). The widespread of Covid-19 pandemic took same manner of movement such as: By air, sea, rail and road through infected persons in Wuhan community in China. Little did anyone know that the disease would find its way into Nigeria, and not only infecting individuals but also, impacted the Hospitality Industry and the economy of Nations. People are constantly on the move from place to place and from one county to another in search of livelihood or greener pastures. Hence, the global spread of the Covid-19. Ohmae, (2005) have stated that in the past, business and economics were like plays performed in separate theatres to discrete audiences. The actors and actresses could be distinct and their manner of performance could be influenced by the individual theatre's tradition. We could associate the spread of the Covid-19 pandemic, as being like plays performed in China and by association through infected individual business travellers have been relocated into other countries of the World; hence, the spread of the disease. Ollor, (2012) stressed that plays could usually be staged in communities for communal benefits during festive periods of the year, such as Christmas periods; but, with the case of Covid-19 pandemic, it came as a disease; a destroyer of businesses and destabilized global activities. Ehiagwina, Anjori, Jimoh, Abiodun & Raji, (2020), have said that Covid-19 is associated with severe acute respiratory syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). According to the authors, the disease was first reported to the World Health Organization (WHO) on December 31, 2019 and on March 11, 2020, was declared Global Pandemic. It is a global pandemic disease in the sense that over 200 countries of the World have been affected and more than 5,000,000 (five million) people have died from the disease. Smith, (2020) stressed that Covid-19 have disrupted all facets of human endeavour, affecting households and families Worldwide. Businesses as well as travels were all affected. Equally affected were the Hotels, Lodging Establishments, Restaurants and Public Markets. There was complete lock-down from the reach of everyone. Individuals were forced to stay at home and be safe from contacting the COVID-19 pandemic. Many employees were laid off from work. Apart from the health hazards and fatalities, the associated economic uncertainties due to lockdown led to massive cost to the economies of various Nations of the World. Ehiagwina, et al., (2020) stated that the United Nations Trade and Development Agency (UNCTAD) have estimated the cost of Coronavirus outbreak to be about \$2 trillion, (UNCTAD, 2020).

Statement of the Problem

When we think of Hospitality Industry, it is not only Hotels and Restaurants. Barrows and Powers, (2009) have said that Hospitality is much broader in scope. Hospitality in itself, is the reception and entertainment of guests, visitors or strangers with liberality and good will. It could include other institutions that offer Accommodations, Food and Beverages for people away from their homes. Hospitality could also be expanded to include, Private Clubs, Casinos, Resorts, Boarding Schools, Hospital Wards, Attractions and Music Entertainment Industry. These sectors are businesses geared toward personal or public profitability, (Ollor, 2021). The outbreak of Coronavirus also known as COVID-19 pandemic with an origin from Wuhan, China, affected the normal activities of everyday living Worldwide. The Hospitality Industry was largely impacted, not only in Nigeria, but all over the World. Some Three-Star and Four-Star Hotels in Port Harcourt, could not check out some of their guests because they were caught-up with the sudden lockdown restrictions. Hence, this Book Chapter

will find out the impact of COVID-19 pandemic on the Hospitality Industry and indeed the effects on the Employees and how the industry bounced back after the relaxation of the restrictions in Nigeria.

Research Objective

The purpose of this research is to theoretically investigate the impact of COVID-19 pandemic on the Hospitality Industry in Nigeria and examine the effects on the Employees and the extent to which the industry has bounced back or recovered after the restrictions and relaxations in Nigeria.

Theoretical Review of Literature

Pandemics

Dan, (2021) a spokesman for the Pan American Health Organization, a regional office of the World Health Organization, have said that a pandemic is basically a global epidemic because it has spread to more than one continent. According to the author, influenza pandemics have struck about three times every century since the 1500s, or roughly every 10-50 years and one between 1957-1958 and another in 1968-1969. The most infamous pandemic flu of the 20th century, according to the author, however, was that of 1918-1919. He went further and said that, an estimated 40 million people died in less than a year. What made the pandemic flu so different from seasonal flu epidemics is that it killed primarily young people of ages 20-45 years.

In terms of COVID-19, it is a global pandemic disease in the sense that over 200 countries of the World have been affected. The World Health Organization, (WHO) Officials were said to have been slow to adopt the word “pandemic. Ghebreyesus, (2020), who is the WHO Director-General, was of the opinion that the decision on whether to declare the disease a pandemic should be based on the assessment of the geographical spread of the virus, the severity of disease, and the impact on the whole society. According to Ehiagwina, et al., (2020) Corona Virus was first reported to the WHO on December, 2019. But, on March 11, 2020, on citing the rapid increase in cases of COVID-19, its spread across more than 100 countries, and death of thousands, Ghebreyesus, (2020) the WHO Director General made the assessment and declared COVID-19 as a ‘Pandemic’. About two days later, the former President of United States of America, Donald Trump announced COVID-19 a National Emergency.

The Pandemic of 1869

The Poem below was written by an anonymous writer in 1869 and printed during 2019 Pandemic. I noticed its devastating effects as compared with Covid-19 Pandemic and thought it wise to include same for readers to reflect on it:

This is Timeless

And people stayed at home and read books

And listened and they rested

And did exercises and made art and played

And learned new ways of being and stopped and listened more deeply

Someone meditated, someone prayed

Someone met their shadow and people began to think differently

And people healed and in the absence of people who lived ignorant ways

Dangerous, meaningless and heartless, the earth also began to heal

And when the danger ended and people found themselves

They grieved for the dead and made new choices

And dreamed of new vision and created new ways of living

And completely healed the earth,

Just as they were healed.

The above Poem reminds me of the current situations with Covid-19 Pandemic where so many people lost their lives, the economy collapsed, most workers lost their jobs, some businesses closed down and many became bankrupt. The whole World was on Lockdown and people were hungry and became restless. In Nigeria, the Youth became restless and started the 'End SAS Protests' which ended with Lotting of some Public and Private shops and some lives were lost. There were physical Distancing, wearing of face masks and periodic hand washing. Ehiagwina, et al., (2020) have emphasized the financial burdens which the Covid-19 and its corresponding 'stay at home' happening at the same time all over the World; and were of the opinion that the economic impacts could be short-term in nature; but, sharp in dept. They therefore, emphasized that the negative consequential effects might spread Worldwide; affecting various aspects of human activities.

The Hospitality Industry

Hospitality Industry according to Reh, (2014); and Gosh(2008) is the friendly reception and generous treatment of customers or strangers. It is one of the oldest industry the World as the first explorers, traders, missionaries, needed lodging, food, drinks and break from their travel. Ollor, (2015) has stressed that Hospitality Industry offers travellers a home away from home. Also, in a wider sense, Hospitality Industry includes any group engaged in Tourism, Entertainment, Transportation, Rental Companies and Tour Operators. And so, what affects Hospitality Industry affects these Companies.

Hospitality is so much more than an industry. It has its core as an art for service, dedication to others, quest for generosity, as well as openness to the World. Hospitality accounts for 10% of global GDP and also accounts for one out of nine jobs World-wide. It is one of the main contributors to the rebound of the World economy and job market recovery, (Domenget, 2020). According to Domenget, (2020), 'Hospitality is the future'. The industry has been one of the sectors most badly impacted by the Covid-19 pandemic. Barely four months into Covid- 19 pandemic, according to Domenget, (2020), over 7.1 million people have been infected globally; which means that, the numbers of people who have died are far too many. The author who could see the future of Hospitality Industry, as the World Trade, declining between 13% and 32%. Also, he opines that, the figures of the actual pandemic might seem unreal and therefore, had call on all Hoteliers to their very core as lives and economies have been impacted as never before.

Gareth, (2020) have said that, in the UK, all pubs, bars and restaurants had to close their doors and shops in order to abide by the unprecedented measures ordered by the Government. Darkwa, (2021), in his report at the Conference of African Universities acknowledged that Covid-19 have disrupted traditional learning system and educational trajectory have been changed on the scale never experienced before which might create new opportunities for Africa to innovate rapidly. Domenget, (2020) in his view, stressed that Sommet Education, which trains Caterers are no exception from the disruptive nature of the Covid-19 pandemic. The Campus Operations were either closed or reduced to the minimum and offering accommodation to the students who could not reach out to their families. According to Jones, (2020) the Hospitality Industry will not be safe until everyone is safe as Covid-19 pandemic has created incredible revolution, disruption, discontinuity and change which the World would experience as never before and with speed. Covid-19 might turn what was regarded as 'normal' upside down which might change the industry's priorities and values; impacting on the way we interact with each other for the foreseeable future.

Being safe might mean, significant improvement on the restrictions on individuals' social, work patterns, and behaviour until vaccines are globally available.

The new variants of Covid-19 (Delta- Variant) have erupted and no one have been able to predict how soon the end of this highly disruptive Delta Variant disease called Covid-19 pandemic. Some researchers have said that Covid-19 might be around us for a while. Ogden, (2021) have said that, since an uncertain road lies ahead, the future prosperity of businesses and workforces might be a major concern. Most of the industry might be facing entire income stream losses. Some businesses might currently be at the verge of prioritizing reduction of costs and cash flow management to stay afloat at this critical period.

Miller, (2020) has stated that life could be 10% of what happens to us and 90% could be how we respond to it. We must therefore, understand, adapt, and respond to happenings around us; knowing that guests might adjust to how they would travel and interact with hotels. Hence, our voices could be raised in favour of the guests, which would provide value for them at this critical period of Covid-19 pandemic. In order to deliver the 'wow' experience, hotels would need to bring together various technologies to ensure that they know their guests on an individual basis; rather than, 'persona-base' level which might require having guests' profile for tracking their behaviour and serving their needs.

Linkages Between Hospitality and Tourism

Source: Mackenzie, M. and Chan, B., (2009). *Tourism and Hospitality Studies: Introduction to Hospitality*.

Figure 1: The Relationship between Hospitality and Tourism.

From the Figure 1 above, Mackenzie and Chan, (2009) explained how Hospitality Industry and Tourism Industry are linked and so were they affected by Covid-19 pandemic. We can also see that the linkages were so much so that when Covid-19 pandemic struck, neither the Hospitality Industry nor the Tourism Industry was spared. The businesses were all impacted and near collapse. Ghebreyesus, (2020) of the World Health Organization stressed regrettably that, with the impact of Covid-19 pandemic on businesses, not all the businesses would survive; because, their current

circumstances could force them to close down. Reuters Survey of Global Business Leaders, (2020) opined that the Hospitality Sector was the most vulnerable with about 41% of CEO’s suggesting that their firms were at risk of not surviving. Ghebreyesus, (2020) the WHO Leader, was of the view that survivals might reinvent themselves through creative and innovative responses with new business approaches which might allow them to develop in the future. Jones,(2020) stressed that his own Report ‘The eHotelier’ was not on ‘how to guide’; but,might help in prompting businesses to think about their own potential solutions.

Mackenzie, and Chan, (2009) also have stressed that, Hospitality Industryis a part of a wider group of economic activities called Tourism which areall not profit-making businesses. The two main sectors in the Hospitality Industry are: Accommodation Establishment and Food and Beverage Establishments.

In the establishments involved inprofit-making include:Accommodations, food and drinks to the individuals who for whatever reasons are away from home. These Sectors were all impacted during the locked-down due to Covid-19 pandemic.

The Accommodation Structure

Source:Mackenzie, M. and Chan, B., (2009). Tourism and Hospitality Studies: Introduction to Hospitality.

Figure 2: The Relationship between Hospitality and Tourism.

Figure 2 above, is the Structure of the Accommodation Establishment in the Hospitality Industry. They include the Non-commercial and the Commercial Accommodations. Both Sectors were impacted by the Covid-19 pandemic; but we will dwell more on the Commercial Accommodations in Hotels in particular.

According to Ollor, (2021), the Covid-19 pandemic was such a difficult time for the Lodging Establishments in Hotels. The industry was the most affected economically by the Covid-19 pandemic lockdown. The Lodging Administrators had to use their initiatives when no revenue was generated during the period. Mill, (2006) have stressed that:‘If a room is not sold in a day, the revenue for that day is lost forever’.

More Linkages Between Hospitality Industry and Tourism

- 1) **Travel/ Tourism Industry:** Most Guests patronize Hospitality businesses through Hospitality Associations or Partnerships. No one is an island; as individuals, we depend on each other for survivals, businesses do the same. They depend on each other for their survival. With this cooperation in mind; many organizations, groups, and even entire Industries assist Hoteliers in serving overnight guests. The transportation industry could help guests travel to and from hotels. Travel agents could assist travelers to select a mode of transportation and give advice about which Hotels could be the best for a specific traveler's needs. Tour operators could assist travel agents in their work. Increasingly, the internet has influenced the way travel industry services are marketed and purchased. When all these links to the Hospitality Industry are broken down due to lock-down associated with Covid-19 pandemic, the Hospitality Industry was highly impacted negatively. Business travelers or individual travelers were no longer able to travel; thereby, the entire systems of the industry were paralyzed.
- 2) **Transportation services:** When a traveler decides to take a trip, one of his first and most important decisions might be his mode of transportation. Accessibility, speed, comfort, and cost might all influence his choice. Generally, the fastest transportation methods might also be the most expensive. Historically, stagecoaches, steamships, and railroads are some of the developed routes that could accommodate mails, freight, and passengers, Ghost, (2009). Today, the most popular forms of passenger transportation are airplanes, buses and automobiles, which likely work closely with Hoteliers. However, these Transport Services were equally on lock-down at the hit of Covid-19 pandemic. As such, the Hospitality Industry were all negatively affected.
- 3) **Airlines:** Airline Travels are the most preferred method for most Leisure and Business Travelers whose destinations could be far from their original place of residence. Airline travel is fast, and its popularity continues to grow. According to Mill, (2006) a U.S. airline could carry more than 500 million passengers per year. The airline industry is a partner with the Hotel Industry. Many travelers flying into airports are picked up by transport shuttles and driven to the Hotels for their accommodations and possible relaxation. In most cases, the shuttle might also return with some travelers back to the airport for their departures, (Mill, 2006). The Hotel shuttles are the vehicles used by hotels to transport guests to their various destinations as well as shopping around for souvenirs and site seeing. When these links are shut-down due to the pandemics, the businesses were shut down and hardship caused by low patronage became the order of the day.
- 4) **Bus Lines:** Buses are important part of the Travel Industry and could have a substantial effect on a hotel's occupancy. They are used for long distance travels by individual travelers than that of airplanes and automobiles. However, buses are used by economy minded travelers and by travelers being shuttled from airports, train stations, and parking areas. For many hoteliers, the most important role played by the bus-lines that transport 'charter travel groups' to hotels are for accommodations, (Hayes, Ninemeier, & Miller, 2014). A charter could mean a form of transportation rented exclusively for a specific group of travelers. Planes and buses could often be chartered for group travels as well. Because these activities were truncated with the Covid-19 pandemic lockdown, businesses were grounded with so much revenue loss.
- 5) **Trains:** Passenger trains still play major roles in public transportation especially leisure travelers and commuters. Hotels located near train stations generate substantial revenue volumes from these passengers. The train system could carry more than 65,000 passengers per day,

(Ghosh, 2008). These passenger trains were all impacted, even in Nigeria by the restrictions due to Covid-19 pandemic and lots of revenues that could have been generated from them by the Hospitality Industry were lost.

- 6) **Rental Cars:** Cars are the most popular method of Travel all over the world and the impact of their drivers and passengers on the Hotel business could be tremendous. Most people who travel by cars use them extensively for short-distance travels. People who travel by air frequently rent cars or other vehicles upon arrivals at their destinations. But, with the Covid-19 pandemic, Car Rental business came to a halt and the businesses virtually closed down and Hospitality Industry was equally impacted. The car rental business had been important part of the transportation industry and consists of all business that rent or lease passenger cars, vans trucks and utility trailers; some of them suffered losses of revenues due to the pandemic lock-down all over the World. Some of these businesses offer only short-term rentals, others only long-term leases and some provide both services. Hoteliers who enjoy a close association with their local car rental businesses often find that travelers renting cars ask for advice about where to stay when they pick up their cars. Therefore, Hotels gain business from rental agency referrals, (Hayes, et. al., 2014).

- 7) **Travel Agents:** Supposing you are planning to have a trip to a place you have never been before, you would likely need the services of an experienced Travel Agent. A travel agent is a professional who assists clients in planning and purchasing Travels. For many travelers, the knowledge and skill of professional travel planner are important to the success of the trip. With the constantly changing airfares and schedules, thousands of available vacation packages, and the vast amount of information available on the Internet can make travel planning frustrating and time consuming. To sort out their travel options, many leisure and business travelers seek the advice of a travel agent, (Mill, 2006) You could use the services of these agents to book business or leisure trips, flights, Hotel rooms, rental cars and tours; but, with Covid-19 pandemic, everyone has been scared of making any arrangements for travelling, and as such, affecting the Hospitality Industry.

Impact Of Covid-19 Pandemic on Hospitality Industry

The Hospitality Industry was one of the sectors in the global economy that was seriously affected by the Covid-19 pandemic; coupled with the lockdown of business areas including the Hospitality Industry. So many people and business organizations virtually obeyed the 'stay at home order'. Some Hotels in Port Harcourt and Nigeria as a whole, were able to cope as some of them were able to increase their revenues as they reduce cost in the following areas:

- 1) **Shutting Down:** The shut-down of businesses and movement restrictions of individuals in Nigeria and indeed, globally; created unusual financial difficult experiences for the service industry such as Hotels and Restaurants Establishments. Also, the shut-down affected Entertainment Industry, Sport activities, public and private Events. Weddings were cancelled or postponed. Restrictions of people's movements and business activities all over the World shocked the World economically as businesses went grounded completely. This was what Macron, (2020) called the global health pandemic; and expressed how economic models have been fractured by global events which might need to be remade by new values and ideas.
- 2) **Increase in Hygiene Practices:** Most Hotels Hotel in Nigeria and globally had to heighten their hygiene practices to be able to contain the fear of contacting and spreading the contagious disease. These involved the frequency at which hotel rooms were mopped, cleaned, and sanitized. Linens were not left out. They were washed and ironed thoroughly to

be able to destroy any trace of the Coronavirus. Cutlery, plates, pots and pans and indeed, the entire kitchen was kept scrupulously clean and sanitized. Walk areas and work surfaces were not left out. For example, stair case rails, reception platform, tables and chairs were all cleaned and sanitized. Ollor and Efenene, (2019) and Ollor, (2015) have emphasized the importance of cleanliness in and around the Hospitality environment. They stressed that waiters and waitresses are like bridges between the kitchen and the guests and so, should be clean all the time. Guests are stronghold of any business; without them, business cannot exist. Food Service involves food safety which means that foods and where foods are produced must be clean and free from any form of contaminations. For this reason, hygiene practices be viewed as important even now at this time of Covid-19 pandemic. The environments where foods are served should equally be cleaned as well.

- 3) **Acquiring Thermometer for Temperature Checks, Hand Sanitizers and Hand Washing Areas:**At the hit of the pandemic, so many Hotels in Port Harcourt had to acquire thermometer for checking body temperatures of the guests right at the door before entering the building. Hand sanitizers were also made available, not only at the door, but also within the room areas. For the hand washing areas, they were all in the vicinity of the guests on arrivals. These were all available so that the guests would feel secure and safe within the hotel.
- 4) **A Number of Employees were laid off or salary reductions:**Some Employee of the Hospitality Industry were either reduced or laid off due to the effects of Covid-19 pandemic as it related to the strict restriction of movement of individuals from both local and International Communities. There was virtually no activity in both in and out the Hospitality areas. Hence, the reduction/lay off of the employees to save some cost. The skeletal services they had were the Isolation Centers created for some of them in other to isolate the Oil Company Workers/ Water Pirates who were returning from their rig; these were just to keep the industry afloat. There was not enough boom as before where guests would normally troop in and out of the Hotels. For the reason of insufficient funds, most Hotels resolved in laying off some of their employees, so as to save some cost. According to Ollor and Tom, (2020) and Mill, (2006) Employees are liquid gold of any organization and as such; they should not be the 'first port of call' when it comes to saving cost for companies. Employees are like assets of a company; they work very hard for the success of the organization and making sure that guests are well taken care of. Therefore, they should be treated with passion and not be thrown out for lack of funds.
- 5) **Maintaining a particular number of guests as allowed by the Covid-19 guidelines in the State:**Just as the number of social gatherings were reduced to 50 persons, so also was the number of guests were reduced to a maximum of 50 guests at a time. The guests must wear face masks; 'NO MASKS, NO ENTRY'. This inscription was fastened at the entrance of the Hotels and social distancing were highly maintained. The number of guests in the hotels became reduced and limited as hotels had to work by the rules in order to stay in business during the relaxed periods of the Covid-19 pandemic. Hence, the reduction in the number of the employees in most Hotels. Some Hotel Administrators found it ideal to generate some revenue within the Lodging facility. They realized business has drastically reduced, and so, accepted the Oil and Gas company workers from rig duties and were placed in isolation in hotel rooms. Room Services were reduced to the benefit of both parties. And so, some revenues were attracted. Few employees who were available attended to the Workers and were unduly over worked.

In the Hospitality Industry, Hayes, Ninemeier and Miller, (2014) have said that, when business is good, average room rates, occupancy percentages and Revenue per available rooms, (RevPARs) would be high. They also expressed that when Hotels are managed well, Gross Operating Profit Per Available Rooms, (GOSPPARs) would be high as well. When these indicators are low, knowledgeable Hoteliers would recognize that business is not as good as when they were. With the global Covid-19 and its impact on the Hospitality Industry, the Hospitality businesses were at ground zero. Macron, (2020) opined that the whole World have been experiencing a revolution which should change our behaviour in the post Covid-19. He stressed that the impact on the Hospitality and Tourism Industry would likely be profound in the short and medium-term. The author also stressed that Covid-19 effect should be likened to the economic downturn where assumptions of recovery were based on the existing models. This is a global health pandemic where models have been fractured by the global events and would need to be remade based on new values and ideas.

Repositioning Hospitality Industry Post Covid-19 Pandemic

Management of Hospitality Industry at a time such as Covid-19 pandemic could be conceptualized and managed as showed in the figure below. Hospitality Industry as a business is Practically oriented Field which if conceptualized, could be effectively managed in four dimensions. Ollor, (2019) have specified that we can conceptualize Hospitality Management using four dimensions since the dimensions share several characteristics with Facility Management.

Fig. 3: The Six Dimensions of Hospitality Management and Covid-19 Pandemic
Adapted from: Ollor, (2019). Hospitality Management Beyond the Kitchen.

Facility Management, according to Ollor, (2019) involves People, Process, Maintenance Infrastructure and Property Management. Reuters Survey of Global Business Leaders, (2020) have described the Hospitality Sector as the most vulnerable in the midst of Covid-19 pandemic. About 41% of CEO’s agreed that their firms were at risk for not survival. They were of the view that a framework for establishing an analysis could be derived. For this study, the acronym chosen were CETTEL. CETTEL represents: Consumer, Economy, Travel, Technology, Environmental and Legal. The analysis would be used in strategic planning for re-prioritize and highlight significant changes which might impact the Hospitality Industry. This idea could be related to what Macron, (2020) expressed concerning economic models which have been fractured by global events which would need to be remade by new values and ideas.

With Covid-19 hitting so hard on the Hospitality Industry, CETTEL would be used to analyze the changes to be expected, Why and How the change would impact on the Hospitality Industry. CETTEL, therefore, represents:

- i. Consumers
- ii. Economy
- iii. Travel
- iv. Technology
- v. Environment and
- vi. Legal

We therefore, will expatiate on the above words individually:

- i. **Consumers:** Ollor, (2007) defined consumers as individuals who purchase products or services for personal use. In this case, Consumers are the guests who patronize the Hospitality Industry by purchasing their products or services in Port Harcourt, Nigeria and indeed, globally. Hospitality has been defined, in reality, as the caring of people in terms of shelter, food and beverages, clothing, beautification of individuals and functions, decorations, entertainments and other activities well packaged. When we are at home, these needs may not be obvious; but they could be prerequisites when we travel from home as Tourists, Business people or Visitors, (Ollor, 2018). According to Leonhardt, (2020), Consumers might have overriding concerns for all aspects of their safety, health and wellbeing which might guide their Choice of Hospitality Industry. He went further and emphasized that there would be need for establishing trust, security and the duty of care should be essential in establishing public confidence in the Hospitality Industry. Employees are equally consumers; and as such, would want to be treated with same safety, health and wellbeing measures like those of the Consumers they are working with. How then would this impact on Hospitality? According to Hunt, (2020) new models and concepts for Hospitality would need to be developed to meet the Consumers' needs for a safe, social and hospitable experience. Empathy with the consumer and emotional intelligence would be exercised for providing the future Hospitality Service and Experience. For the Employees, greater autonomy and empowerment would be needed to manage and enhance Employees' confidence.
- ii. **Economy:** Economy as defined by Hornby, (2015) is the relationship production, trade and supply of money in a particular country or region. In this event, it concerns financial performance of the Hospitality Industry in the midst of Covid-19 pandemic. Barrett, (2020) have expressed how the pandemic has caused massive disruption and fracturing the existing economic models of all countries, institutions and governance models they relied on. He stressed that the models will no longer be feasible and so, new and different economic model should emerge base on the new realities and societal values. In the Hospitality Industry, there have been major shifts and reduction in demand for some products and services which have affected revenue supplies. Barrett, (2020) indicated that the Service Sectors, which Hospitality Industry belongs to and with high levels of direct customer interactions might have significant short – medium term drops in demand which might lead to business closures and redundancies. In this way, Hospitality would be affected by confidence, public debt and weakening of Consumer spending. Therefore, Hospitality Industry would need new collaborative approaches between businesses to develop cooperation and interdependency for survival and re-establish confidence. For

the Hospitality Industry with high debt ratios, expensive leases and high operating costs, would need to be dropped because of the reduced period of demand. New form of mode might be required with the owners, leaseholder, funders, franchises and operators. Short-term investment cycles need to be considered to reflect new elements of risk and potential returns. Implementation of physical distancing measures and wearing of facemasks in public places might become new normal and therefore, income with high volume. According to Lopez, (2020), by these changes, new leaders would emerge and would create entrepreneurial and resilient, with strong ethical and moral values and resonate with the post Covid-19 World and those leaders who would cling to old leadership might be flushed out.

- iii. **Travel:** Meir, (2020) has emphasized that the previous patterns of global Travel might not return. This might have been that governments-imposed restrictions on public movements and so consumer sentiment and safety concerns became the overriding principle in decisions making for air travels. In his view of the author, business travel would be reduced and impact on the large international events. People would be reluctant to travel and mix with large group of people. Cruise Liners were implicated in the spread of the virus and have received global attention. For these reasons, current density and profile of passengers on Cruise operations might make safety, wellbeing and health of passengers extremely difficult. This would lead to reduction in passenger numbers, revenues and long-term financial sustainability. This impact would surely affect the Hospitality Industry considering their relationships. Ollor, (2015) have stressed that Hospitality Industry gets their Consumers by receiving and accommodation those who have travelled from far and near into their facilities. Hospitality businesses with reliance on international events, such as: Trade exhibitions, meetings and sporting events would need to gain public confidence in safety factors in Travel and destination management. As part of confidence building measure, Resorts and Cruise Liners would be improved.
- iv. **Technology:** Doubree, (2020) have stated that the lessons learnt from the pandemic was that, there have not been any drop in productivity and that some practices have improved, such as communication which are more regular and efficient remotely. The author further stressed that technology have been embraced by new uses and have become ways of working. The pandemic has acted in a way as a catalyst to innovations, cooperation, speed and creativity of the users. The author emphasized how governments and individuals have come to rely on digital technologies in their forced changes in behaviour, processes, systems and work practices. Users have become efficient and effective in understanding the capabilities of the technology and are exploring their use in creative ways. People and companies operating web sites that allow traveler to book Hotel rooms online are increasingly important partners to Hoteliers. Online Travel Agents, (OTA) sites are increasingly popular with travelers, (Mill, 2006). Online Travel Agent is an organization that provides travel booking services on the Internet. Hotel Managers can create their own web sites and sell their room directly to consumers who use the Internet to reserve rooms. Hotels utilize intermediary web sites such as Travelocity which sell Hotel rooms online for numerous Hotel companies. Consumers also visit these sites to compare prices, hotel features and location before making hotel selection. Just as Hotel companies have historically relied on Travel Agents to sell their hotel rooms, the Hoteliers also relied on the OTA to sell their hotel rooms. Doubree, (2020), emphasized that increased emphasis on communication technologies as a means of business interaction would reduce the need

for business travel and impact in some back-office operations that could have been carried out from home.

- v. **Environmental:** The quality of the global environment should be improved significantly in the midst of pandemic because of the changes in work patterns, local restrictions on movements, less transport use and less air travel, (Graffiti, 2020). There would a shift in public sentiment in recognizing the improvements and connections with the environment and how the environment would impact on their own health and wellbeing. All forms of pollution including noise should be reduced. This has sharply evidenced the human impact on the environment during the pandemic. Through almost a freeze on human activity the world would see the biggest annual drop in recorded carbon emissions. Which would suggest that society would be looking at the environmental sustainability in a more critical and informed way that would influence consumer behavior and values as well as political interventions. The Hospitality Operations would be more cognizant of the environmental and sustainability issues knowing that the pandemic has highlighted the fragility of the global environment. Graffiti, (2020) opined that some commentators referred to the fragility of the global environment as the “Wake-Up Call”. The sustainability movement would be amplified and accelerated; Consumers would be reassured of their Hospitable experiences which would not adversely impact on the environment.
- vi. **Legal:** Government would establish new regulations and controls on my aspects of life, such as: Health Care, Health and Safety and risk which would apply to all operations, travel, public gatherings and retail operations; which would include licensing for maximum numbers. These could include legally defining social and physical distancing. Visa regulations and health controls would change and would impact on the free movement of people leading to possible quarantine and other health restrictions as imposed by some countries. New hygiene and sanitation regulation would impact on all the hospitality operational practices, which would include imposed cleaning regimes to meet new safety and operational standards, and enhanced protection measures for employees. The base assumption which could be that anyone using Hospitality premises could be a carrier of the disease, therefore, the cleaning protocols would reflect that assumption; but could delay in bringing the facilities back into operation and would also have cost implications.

Conclusions

Covid-19 pandemic was a ‘mixed blessing’. The pandemic exposed Nigeria’s poor health facilities and organization. It also brought Nigeria into the limelight of the world in terms of health resources, especially the development and manufacture of vaccines, which was not in insistence.

The Hospitality Industry adapted to the general lock-down and restrictions of economic activities through e-commerce. For example, my family regularly placed orders to our favourite restaurant and our orders were delivered to our home and we made payment by e-transfers.

Most Hotels adapted to the general lockdown and restrictions by becoming Quarantine Centres for Off-shore workers in the oil industry. Most Oil companies hired Hotels where their Off-shore workers resided for two weeks in rotation between working Off-shore and being quarantined.

While the Covid-19 pandemic is still disrupting economic activities, Nigeria, like many other countries, has resumed hosting Big Sports Events, such as the National Sports Festival which held in Edo State, by careful implementation of public health and hygiene measures. Such resumptions of Sports and other Big Events have helped in re-bouncing the Hospitality Industry.

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